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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

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Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra

Dr. Ajitha T S¹

Abstract

Almost all the ancient dynasties of kings had the practice of constructing harems for their women. It was expected to be an abode of women where they could enjoy utmost freedom. Was that a place of peace and happiness? What was the status of women in royal harem? These questions lead to the 34 th chapter of the *Nāṭyaśāstra*, where a detailed description of the female inmates of the royal harem is given. This paper tries to evaluate the description of the inmates of harem given in *Nāṭyaśāstra* in light of the real-life situation provided in - *Mālavikāgnimitra*.

Key words- Ancient Indian society- women life- harem-patriarchy- *Nāṭyaśāstra*- Kālidāsa- *Mālavikāgnimitra*

Introduction

The position of women in India has long been a subject of intense debate. Some argue that ancient Indian texts glorify womanhood and suggest that India offers a sacred and revered status for women. In contrast, others cite literature and historical accounts to argue that patriarchal structures have long subjugated women. Sanskrit literature, while not providing extensive commentary on women's roles, does contain references that help us infer their status. During times characterized by polygamy and autocracy, kings were often regarded as divine figures, and women's lives were largely dedicated to serve them. The *anṭhpura*—a palace where women associated with the king resided—was situated behind the royal palace, with the army stationed between the *anṭhpura* and the royal quarters. For

1 Associate Professor, Dept. of Sanskrit, Sri. C. Achutha Menon Govt. College, Thrissur

security reasons, queens chosen to spend time with the king were summoned to the royal palace, and their movement was highly restricted. They were closely monitored, akin to prisoners, and were confined to specific areas assigned to them. This paper aims to examine the social situation reflected in the 34th chapter of the *Nāṭyaśāstra* and analyze its depiction in Kālidāsa's *Mālavikāgnimitra*.

According to Kauṭilya, 80 men and 50 women were appointed to various duties to protect the anthpura. Although the king employed prostitutes in numerous roles, they were prohibited from entering the anthpura and mingling with the royal women. Only those who were tested for their purity and faithfulness were allowed access to the anthpura. Top of ForBottom of FormThe 34th chapter of the *Nāṭyaśāstra* provides a detailed description of the female inmates of the royal harem. In the male-dominated society of the time, strict rules and protocols governed the lives of those within the harem. *Mālavikāgnimitra*, widely accepted as the first drama written by Kālidāsa, centers on the budding romance between King Agnimitra and Mālavikā, a female attendant. Although the drama primarily focuses on the king and his emotions, Kālidāsa skillfully portrays the emotional and material aspects of the **anthpura**. The play reveals the complexities and frustrations within the female world of the harem. Dhāriṇī and Irāvati, who have a conjugal relationship with the king, hold prominent positions within the **anthpura**, and all female attendants connected to the king's life play roles in the narrative.

The Structure of a Royal Harem

The arrangement of a royal harem primarily depends on the relationships of its inmates with the king. In an era of polygamy, kings often had relationships with multiple women simultaneously. Such arrangements posed security risks, as royal women could potentially harm the monarch. Therefore, security officials were vigilant in monitoring and testing the loyalty of women in the king's proximity.

For convenience and security, these women were housed in a single building known as the harem (anthpura), which was equipped with all necessary facilities. Women were invited to the royal palace

based on the king's wishes, but after their meetings, they had to return to the harem. Thus, the female world was largely confined to the harem, with visits to the royal palace offering only brief respite from this confinement. The authorities ensured that the needs of the harem were met and employed loyal male servants and transgender individuals to attend to various needs. These attendants often served as spies rather than mere servants. Within the harem, a hierarchical structure was observed, influenced by factors such as wealth, sacrificial rights, beauty, and the birth of a son. The *Nāṭyaśāstra* depicts this hierarchy, categorizing female inmates into two main groups:

1. **Royal Women:** Women directly connected with the king.
2. **Women Attendants:** Those skilled in soft skills and art forms.

The *Nāṭyaśāstra* provides a detailed classification of the harem's occupants based on their relationship with the king. Here is an analysis of the titles attributed to the inmates:

Royal Women

1. **Mahādevi (Chief Queen):** The Mahādevi was the most prestigious inmate of the harem, commanding respect and authority from other women. This title was conferred upon a woman only after consecration, signifying her esteemed position in the kingdom. She was entitled to share the throne with the king and participate in all sacrificial ceremonies. The Mahādevi was expected to possess qualities such as aristocratic heritage, physical attractiveness, a pleasing nature, positive attitude, mature behavior, composure, unconditional love for the king, and empathy toward royal decisions.
2. **Devis (Other Queens):** These women were members of royal families but lacked the formal consecration that elevated them to the Mahādevi's status. They were proud of their lineage, appearance, and the affection they received from the king. Their status often led to jealousy towards their rivals and a preoccupation with maintaining their attractiveness.
3. **Swāminī (Highborn Wives):** Swāminīs were daughters of high-ranking officials who were given elevated positions within the harem as a reward for their charm. They were distinguished by

- their noble lineage and the king's recognition of their appeal.
4. **Sthāyini (Ordinary Wives):** This group consisted of women valued for their physical charm, proficiency in amorous acts, alertness, good behavior, and youth. They often experienced jealousy towards their rivals within the harem.
 5. **Bhagini (Concubines):** Bhagini were attentive to the king's desires and were known for their lack of jealousy and demands. They were characterized by their humility, forbearance, and attractiveness.

Woman Attendants

Despite residing in the harem, these women had specific roles to serve the king and queens. Here is a detailed description of the different categories of woman attendants:

1. **Śilpakārikās (Craftswomen):** These women excelled in soft skills, arts, and crafts. Their specialties included perfume making, painting, and interior design.
2. **Nāṭakīyas (Actresses):** Nāṭakīyas were women with artistic talent, skilled in acting, music, and playing musical instruments. They were known for their physical charm and positive attitude.
3. **Nartakīs (Dancers):** Nartakīs were proficient in 64 arts, including dancing and music. They were recognized for their training, physical appearance, and skill in performing arts.
4. **Anucārikas (Maids):** Anucārikas were loyal maids dedicated to serving the king in various circumstances.
5. **Paricārika (Maids for Special Tasks):** These maids were specifically appointed to assist the king with his comforts and personal care.
6. **Samcārika (Sentries):** Samcārikas patrolled the palace and its surroundings, signaling time with bells. They were excluded from sexual pleasures.
7. **Preṣaṇacārika (Errand Girls):** These women were dispatched on confidential missions and errands.
8. **Mahattaras (Matron):** Mahattaras were responsible for the protection of the harem and were actively involved in ceremonies and prayers to secure divine favor for the king.
9. **Kumāris (Maidens):** Kumāris were young, attractive girls kept away from romantic entanglements. Their youth and merits

made them notable within the harem.

10. Vṛddhas (Old Ladies): Vṛddhas were experienced and knowledgeable about royal affairs, having interacted with many people throughout their lives.
11. Ayuktikas (Female Overseers): Ayuktikas managed various aspects of the harem's inventory, including stores, weapons, perfumes, food, grains, jewels, and clothes. They also inspected the food prepared for the king.

This classification highlights the diverse roles and responsibilities of women within the harem, reflecting their contributions to the functioning and security of the royal household.

Evaluation of Custom and Conclusion

To understand the structure and hierarchy of the female inmates in the anṭhapura as described in the *Nāṭyaśāstra*, it is useful to compare it with the portrayal in *Mālavikāgnimitra*. By comparing these descriptions with their portrayal in *Mālavikāgnimitra*, we can gain insights into how these classifications and roles were reflected in the narrative and social dynamics of the time. Bharata's classification of royal women includes all the king's wives, each holding a specific status within the harem. Among these, the Mahādevī occupies the highest position, not because of the affection she receives from the king, but due to the power and respect conferred by her consecration. The Devis, on the other hand, experience a sense of insecurity due to their lack of consecration. They often live in jealousy and misery, feeling subjugated by the Mahādevī's supremacy. Devis are usually brought to the harem through political alliances and are proud of their royal lineage but remain helpless compared to the Mahādevī. The Sthāyinī, Swāminī, and Bhoginī are included in the harem primarily for their beauty. Their status is contingent on the king's interest, making them eager to please him. Among these, the Bhoginī is characterized by her complete devotion to the king, serving without greed or jealousy and accepting her co-wives' rights. According to Altekar, polygamy was a sign of extravagance among the wealthy and ruling classes. Kings used these numerous matrimonial alliances to extend their political influence. The fate

of princesses after marriage, however, is less clear; they are often forced to adapt to life within the harem alongside others. In the *Rāmāyaṇa*, Kausalya is portrayed as the Mahādevi, Kaikeyi as a Devi, and Sumithra as a Sthāyini. Mandhara's remarks about King Daśaratha's harem reveal the turbulence that can arise. Kaikeyi fears that Kausalya, after becoming Rājamātā, will seek revenge for past insults. This insecurity among the women in the harem ultimately leads to Rāma's exile. In *Mahābhārata* also polygamy is described in a subtle way.

In *Mālavikāgnimitra*, Kālidāsa vividly depicts the various types of women within the harem. Dhāriṇi, an exemplary Mahādevi, enjoys the privilege of being the mother of a royal heir. She accepts the king's other wives and remains composed, focusing more on the lineage of Mālavikā than on her own status. Dhāriṇi is a figure of high resolve, responsible for managing the harem and disciplining its members. Irāvati, a Devi, is deeply troubled by the king's new affection for Mālavikā. Her jealousy and immaturity drive her to act against the new girl and report her concerns to Dhāriṇi. Irāvati's behavior presents a negative aspect within the drama. Several female attendants in the play include:

- *Kaumudikā* and *Bakulāvalikā*, the Preṣaṇacārikas, who handle confidential messages and provide insights into palace events.
- *Paṇḍitakausikī*, a Vṛddha, holds a revered position in the harem and royal court.
- *Nāgarikā*, *Nipuṇikā*, and *Madhukarikā* are Paricārikas serving Dhāriṇi, Irāvati, and Paṇḍitakausikī respectively.
- *Parabhritikā*, the garden caretaker, is a Samcārika.
- *Jayasena*, the Pratihāri, is a Mahattara.

Mālavikā, initially a Kumāri and later promoted to Nartakī, rises within the harem due to her beauty and talent. Her romance with the king attracts the attention of other characters, who are intrigued by the unfolding events.

While the drama centers on a passionate love story, it also explores the emotional complexities of the harem. Even King Agnimitra,

despite his generosity, cannot maintain equal respect for all his wives. His inability to remain faithful highlights how the harem, designed by men, becomes a form of confinement. Women, taught to accept patriarchy, remain loyal to their one and only lord, reflecting the systemic nature of their societal roles. To sum up, the drama portrays a world of women centered around the king. These women, gathered from various places for different reasons, are strategically placed and governed. Despite the appearance of benevolent sexism, which may grant some women limited power, the system ultimately keeps them under the control of patriarchy. The women, constantly striving to please the king and often competing with one another, lead a life of misery and are denied the opportunity to discover their own purpose. Their lives are predetermined by societal norms, and they are compelled to accept and endure their prescribed fates.

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